

Source Classification Taxonomy for Virtual Reconstructions

Draft Version 0.2.0

March 2026

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Preamble

Virtual reconstructions in the fields of architecture, archaeology, and cultural heritage are based on a variety of sources and arguments that should be documented in a comprehensible manner (paradata). A comprehensive, standardized classification of sources tailored explicitly for virtual reconstructions would greatly facilitate the creation of comparable and objective documentation. To this end, a hierarchical classification scheme of sources with seven primary categories has been developed, which is based on existing vocabularies and experiences from real projects. Each source can be further described using objective criteria (e.g., source type, context of origin, scale).

To describe the sources in a more detailed manner, attributes can be added to the individual source types. Attributes can have different types of values, which are:

- Single selection (S),
- Multi selection (M),
- Yes/No (B),
- Text entry (T).

If a value is not explicitly selected or provided by the user, then it is assumed that the information is unknown.

1. Photographs and Films			
Source type	Attribute	Values	Applicable to
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Photograph • Motion picture film 	What is depicted? (M)	Interior • Exterior • Movable object • Urban space • Event • Architectural component • Sculpture • Topography • Building remains • Feature • Sediment • Manufacturing process	All
	Intention (M)	Without direct intention • Building survey/presentation of features • Presentation of findings • Documentation • Artistic representation	All
	State of preservation (source) (M)	Preserved • Handed down • Accessible • Complete • Partial • Original examined	All
	Coloured (S)	Black/white • Coloured • Colour	All
	Aerial photograph (S)	Drone-supported • Aeroplane • Satellite	All
	Perspective / Orthogonal (S)	Perspective • Orthogonal • Orthomosaic	All
	Carrier (M)	Digital • Paper deduction • Glass plate • Negative • Slide positive	All
	Panorama (T)	Degree value	All
	Mono / Stereo (S)	Monoscopic • Stereoscopic	All

2. Technical Illustrations of Buildings and of Movable Objects			
Source type	Attribute	Values	Applicable to
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Floor plan / ground plan • Section / profile • Elevation • Perspective 	What is depicted? (M)	Interior • Exterior • Movable object • Urban space • Event • Architecture component • Sculpture • Topography	All
	Intention (M)	Preliminary design • Construction plan • Design or construction plan • General planning document • Reconstruction • Building survey/ presentation of features • Presentation of findings • Documentation • Artistic documentation or representation • Functional representation • Simulation	All
	State of preservation (source) (M)	Preserved • Handed down • Accessible • Complete • Partial • Original examined	All
	Information on colours / materiality (M)	Colours • Materiality	All
	Freehand sketch (B)	Yes • No	All
	Plan designation (B)	Yes • No	All
	Dimensioned (B)	Yes • No	All
	Vectorised (B)	Yes • No	All
	Scale bar (B)	Yes • No	All
	Scale (B,T)	Yes • No + Number	All
	Intersection line (B)	Yes • No	All
	Plan stamp (B)	Yes • No	All
	To scale (B)	Yes • No	All
	Coloured (B)	Yes • No	All
	Detailed plan (B)	Yes • No	All
	Height specifications (B)	Yes • No	Floor plan / ground plan
	North arrow (B)	Yes • No	Floor plan / ground plan
	Unfolding (B)	Yes • No	Elevation
	Type of section (S)	Building section • Stratigraphy • Archaeological profile • Hydrological profile	Section / profile
	Perspective type (S)	Axonometry • Isometry • Vanishing point drawing • Exploded view	Perspective

3. City Representations / Maps / Terrain			
Source type	Attribute	Values	Applicable to
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City map • Geographical map • Cityscapes • Terrain representations 	What is depicted? (M)	Interior • Exterior • Movable object • Urban space • Event • Architecture component • Sculpture • Topography	All
	Intention (M)	Preliminary design • Construction plan • Design or construction plan • General planning document • Reconstruction • Building survey/ presentation of features • Presentation of findings • Documentation • Artistic documentation or representation • Simulation	All
	State of preservation (source) (M)	Preserved • Handed down • Accessible • Complete • Partial • Original examined	All
	Information on colours / materiality (M)	Colours • Materiality	All
	Type of drawing (S)	Technical drawing • Freehand sketch	All
	Plan designation (B)	Yes • No	All
	Dimensioned (B)	Yes • No	All
	Vectorised (B)	Yes • No	All
	Scale bar (B)	Yes • No	All
	Scale (B,T)	Yes • No + Number	All
	Intersection line (B)	Yes • No	All
	Plan stamp (B)	Yes • No	All
	To scale (B)	Yes • No	All
	Coloured (B)	Yes • No	All
	Detailed plan (B)	Yes • No	All
	Height specifications (B)	Yes • No	All
	Orthogonal / Perspective (S)	Orthogonal • Perspective	All
	North arrow (B)	Yes • No	City map, Cityscapes, Geographical map
	Type of city map	Site plan • Cadastral map • Thematic map	City map
	Type of terrain representation	Stratigraphy • Archaeological profile • Hydrological profile	Terrain representation

4. 3D Models and their Representations			
Source type	Attribute	Values	Applicable to
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical model • Digital model 	What is depicted? (M)	Interior • Exterior • Movable object • Urban space • Event • Architecture component • Sculpture • Topography	All
	Intention (S)	Building survey/presentation of features • Presentation of findings • Documentation • Design model • BIM model • Reconstruction • Artistic documentation or representation • Simulation	All
	Information on colours / materiality (M)	Colours • Materiality	All
	Scale (B,T)	Yes • No + Number	Physical model
	Preservation / Accessible (M)	Preserved • Handed down • Accessible • Photo • Film • Original examined	Physical Model
	Preservation / Digital accessible (M)	Data set preserved • Software preserved • Necessary hardware preserved • Open source	Digital Model
	Digital born (M)	Solid model • Surface model	Digital Model
	Digitalisation (M)	Laser scan • SfM • LiDAR	Digital Model
	Representation (M)	Single image • Animation • Real-time model • AR • VR • MR • Panorama	Digital Model
	Simulation (M)	Light • Sound • Smell • Events • Mechanics • Visibility • Temperature • Geometry • Statics	All

5. Written and Oral Descriptions			
Source type	Attribute	Values	Applicable to
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report / Documentation • Literary text • Record / Administrative document • Inscription / Label / Marking • Scientific text • Treatise • Oral history • Other 	What is depicted? (M)	Interior • Exterior • Movable object • Urban space • Event • Architecture component • Sculpture • Topography	All
	Intention (S)	Description • Building survey/ description of features • Description of findings • Planning documents • Reconstruction • Administrative action	All
	State of preservation (source) (M)	Preserved • Handed down • Accessible • Complete • Partial • Original examined	All
	Information on colours / materiality (M)	Colours • Materiality	All
	Format (M)	Typewritten • Handwritten • Audio recording • Film recording • Digital • Digitised • Machine-readable	All
	Language (T)	Text	All
	Text font (T)	Text	All
	Type of oral history (M)	Interview • Lecture • Eyewitness report	Oral history
	Type of literary text (M)	Prose • Poetry • Building description • Travel report • Correspondence • Autobiography	Literary text
	Type of report (M)	Meeting minutes • Monument preservation report • Session report • Press release • Excavation report	Report / Documentation
Type of record / administrative document	File • Invoice • Charter	Record / Administrative document	

6. Artistic Representations			
Source type	Attribute	Values	Applicable to
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2D • 3D 	What is depicted? (M)	Interior • Exterior • Movable object • Urban space • Event • Architecture component • Sculpture • Topography	All
	Intention (S)	Artistic representation (fixed)	All
	State of preservation (source) (M)	Preserved • Handed down • Accessible • Complete • Partial • Original examined	All
	Coloured (B)	Yes • No	All
	Type of 2D representation (M)	Painting • Drawing • Fresco • Hand sketch • Print • Manuscript illumination • Vase painting • Porcelain painting • Stained glass • Mosaic • Inlay • Collage • Stage design • Wallpaper • Textile art • Graffiti • Coin • Medal • Seal • Other	2D
	Type of 3D representation (M)	Sculpture • Miniature (sculpture) • Small sculpture • Relief • Furniture • Liturgical object • Metal work • Model • Vessels • Household urn • Other	3D
	Materials (T)	Text	All
	Artist signature (B)	Yes • No	All

7. Sampling / Testing / Computation			
Source type	Attribute	Values	Applicable to
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age determination • Material analysis • Geophysical prospection / method • Remote sensing / UAV • Computation / Simulation 	What is depicted? (M)	Interior • Exterior • Movable object • Urban space • Event • Architecture component • Sculpture • Topography	All
	Intention (M)	Description • Building survey/ description of features • Presentation of findings • Documentation • Planning documents • Reconstruction • Administrative action	All
	State of preservation (source) (M)	Preserved • Handed down • Accessible • Complete • Partial • Original examined	All
	Type of sampling (M)	Core drilling • Feature sample • Surface collection • Coming from an artefact	All
	Result format (M)	Text • Plan • Drawing • Image • Interview • Diagram • Film	All
	Type of age determination (M)	OSL • C14	Age determination
	Type of material analysis (M)	Gene analysis • Chemical or mineralogical analysis • X-ray examination • Microscopic analysis • Isotopy (botany, zoology, anthropology, mineralogy)	Material analysis
	Type of geophysical prospection (M)	Ground-penetrating radar (GPR) • Electromagnetics • Resistivity • Magnetometry or Susceptibility • Sonar • Seismics	Geophysical prospection / method
	Type of remote sensing / UAV (M)	LiDAR • Multispectral • Infrared • Radar	Remote sensing / UAV
	Type of computation / simulation (T)	Text	Computation / Simulation